

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Automated Salted Egg Production: An Arduino-Based System for Optimized Salting and Temperature Control

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Abstract

Background: Traditional salted egg production relies on uncontrolled environmental conditions, resulting in long fermentation periods (20–40 days) and inconsistent product quality due to seasonal temperature variations and uneven salt penetration. Although recent studies have introduced PLC- and microcontroller-based automation in food processing, limited research has focused on integrating temperature regulation and salinity control within a low-cost, community-scale system specifically for salted egg production. **Objectives:** This study aimed to (1) design and develop an Arduino-based automated salted egg production device; (2) implement controlled temperature stabilization and standardized salinity regulation during fermentation; and (3) evaluate the usability and acceptability of the developed system using the System Usability Scale (SUS). **Method:** The study developed an Arduino-based automated salted egg production system designed to regulate fermentation temperature and brine salinity in a controlled environment. The system integrates an Arduino AtMega microcontroller, thermocouple sensor, PTC heater, real-time clock (RTC) module, stepper motor, water pump, relay modules, and LCD display to automate brining, temperature stabilization, and fermentation monitoring. Experimental evaluation was conducted over a 25-day fermentation period using duck eggs immersed in 10%, 15%, 20%, and 25% brine solutions at a 1:1 egg-to-brine ratio while maintaining a constant temperature of 25 °C. System usability was assessed using the System Usability Scale (SUS) with 20 members of a local farmers' association. **Findings:** Results demonstrated that the developed system successfully maintained stable fermentation conditions and reduced processing time from 40 days to 25 days, representing a 37.5% reduction. The system achieved a SUS score of 85.0, classified as "Very Good," indicating high usability and user acceptance. **Novelty:** The study introduces a low-cost, temperature- and salinity-controlled fermentation system tailored for community-scale salted egg production. By integrating environmental control, automation, and usability evaluation, the proposed system offers a practical and scalable solution for improving productivity, consistency, and modernization in traditional food processing.

Keywords: Arduino-based system; salted egg production; temperature control; food processing automation

1 Introduction

Salted egg is a traditional preserved food widely consumed in many Asian countries, including the Philippines, where it is locally known as *itlog na maalat*. The product is commonly prepared by immersing duck eggs in saline solution or coating them with a salt-soil paste. Although this method is simple and low-cost, traditional production remains highly dependent on ambient environmental conditions. Fermentation typically requires 20–40 days, and processing duration varies according to seasonal temperature fluctuations. Such uncontrolled conditions often lead to inconsistent salt penetration, prolonged production cycles, and variability in product quality. Recent research on salted egg processing has discussed emerging innovations aimed at improving efficiency and quality. A review on salted egg production processes and quality formation highlighted the limitations of traditional pickling methods and explored innovative rapid processing technologies such as pulsed pressure pickling and physical treatments that reduce production time and improve product quality⁽¹⁾. Advanced analytical techniques like Raman spectroscopy have been applied to monitor brining dynamics and demonstrate how higher salt concentration or adjuncts such as wine can accelerate the brining process, potentially shortening the traditional 30-day curing period to 20–25 days⁽²⁾. Novel curing agents such as ammonium chloride have also been shown to reduce the curing cycle from 28 days to 21 days and improve the physicochemical quality of salted egg yolks, emphasizing the importance of controlled process optimization⁽³⁾.

In addition to product-centric innovations, automation technologies have increasingly been explored in food processing applications. A PLC-based salted egg production device utilizing osmotic pressure principles demonstrated improved process control and reduced manual intervention, though its reliance on industrial-grade controllers may limit accessibility for small-scale producers⁽⁴⁾. Similarly, microcontroller-based food process monitoring systems have shown potential for maintaining stable environmental parameters such as temperature and humidity, supporting real-time supervision and improving product consistency⁽⁵⁾. IoT-based monitoring systems applied to traditional food processing, including salted egg and salted fish production, have also demonstrated enhanced parameter tracking and process transparency, enabling data-driven optimization⁽⁶⁾. Broader technological advancements in smart fermentation systems further indicate that real-time monitoring through sensors, IoT integration, and data analytics can significantly enhance consistency, scalability, and production efficiency⁽⁷⁾. Comparative studies utilizing innovative salting methods such as pressure-ultrasonic pickling have demonstrated significantly reduced curing times compared to conventional immersion techniques, reinforcing the importance of controlled physical interventions in accelerating salting dynamics⁽⁸⁾. Despite these advances, most existing studies focus on optimizing pickling mechanisms, analytical characterization of product quality, or industrial-level automation systems. Limited research has explored the integration of temperature-controlled fermentation and salinity-regulated brining within a single, low-cost microcontroller-based platform specifically for rural and small-scale producers. While PLC-based automation systems provide precision and reliability, their higher cost and complexity reduce accessibility in community-based production settings⁽⁴⁾. Therefore, a research gap persists in developing an affordable, user-friendly automation platform capable of maintaining stable fermentation temperature and salinity in a controlled environment while remaining economically viable for small-scale implementation. To address this gap, this study proposes an Arduino-based automated salted egg production system that integrates temperature regulation, standardized salinity management, and real-time monitoring within a unified platform. Unlike conventional manual methods that rely on passive diffusion and ambient conditions, the proposed system actively maintains a fermentation temperature of 25 °C and ensures consistent brine concentration and egg-to-brine ratio. By regulating these critical parameters, the system aims to reduce processing time, improve product consistency, and enhance operational efficiency. The proposed model addresses three major problems:

1. Prolonged and season-dependent fermentation duration;
2. Inconsistent product quality due to uncontrolled environmental conditions; and
3. Limited access to affordable automation technologies for small-scale producers.

The novelty of this study lies in integrating temperature-controlled fermentation and salinity-regulated brining using a low-cost Arduino platform with automated heating, pumping, and real-time monitoring mechanisms. Additionally, the study incorporates a System Usability Scale (SUS) evaluation involving members of a local farmers' association to assess both technical performance and community-level acceptability. Specifically, this research aims to:

1. Design and develop an Arduino-based automated device for salted egg production;
2. Implement controlled temperature and salinity regulation during fermentation; and
3. Evaluate the usability and acceptability of the developed system using the System Usability Scale.

2 Methodology

2.1 Salted Egg Production Device

A schematic diagram of the device is shown in Figure 1. It depicts how the sensors, and other modules are attached in the microcontroller. Each module is assigned to Analog and Digital pins or the Arduino microcontroller to perform different tasks. As shown in Figure 2, the researchers also developed an initial design before developing the actual device.

Fig 1. Schematic Diagram

2.2 Modules used

- **Breadboard.** It helps on connections of the pins and circuits in to the device
- **Arduino.** This reads the code inputs of all components used in the device.
- **12V charger.** Primary power source of the device which power up the 12V fan and stepper motor, and Arduino.
- **220V plug.** Primary source of our PTC heater plate element to boiled a water.
- **2x 16X2 LCD.** Monitor the measured temperature while fermenting the salted egg and display the current date and time.

Fig 2. Initial Device Design **Legend:** A. LCD 1 – Displaying the temperature in fermenting the salted egg. B. Fan – Controlling the heat temperature inside the box. C. Start Button – To start the all components of the device. D. Flavoring Buttons – To choose what flavor you desire in fermenting in salted egg. E. 15x LED – Represent the number of days in fermenting of salted egg. F. LCD 2 – Displaying the current date and time. G. 5x Heater – To boiled and cook the salted egg. H. Tank – The storage of fermenting solution of salted egg. I. Stepper motor – To lift the screen if the fermenting is done. J. Screen – To hold the egg for soaking.

- **15X LED.** Indicating the Number of days in fermentation the egg.
- **PTC heater Plate.** A heater with a positive temperature coefficient (PTC), often known as a self-regulating heater, has a resistance that rises dramatically with temperature.
- **Stepper Motor.** To lift the screen when the fermenting process is done
- **Real Time Clock (RTC).** It is an electronic component that measures date and time.
- **8 Channel Relay and 4 channel Relay.** It helps to control the PTC Heater element and water pump.
- **5V Water Pump.** Suction method which drain the water through its inlet and released it through the outlet.
- **Thermocouple Sensor.** A sensor to measure the temperature while fermenting the salted egg
- **12V Fan.** It helps to control the temperature inside the device.

2.3 Device Validation Test

2.3.1. Evaluators

The respondents of the study consist of twenty (20) personnel from the Cagbonga Backyard Swine and Duck Breeders Association (CBSDBA). These evaluators assessed the usability, functionality, and effectiveness of the developed Arduino microcontroller-based salted egg production device.

2.3.2. Evaluation

The developed hardware was evaluated using the System Usability Scale (SUS), a widely used instrument for measuring system usability and user experience in modern technology assessments. The SUS questionnaire consists of ten statements rated on a five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. These items allow respondents to evaluate important usability aspects such as ease of use, efficiency, learnability, and overall user satisfaction. The SUS has been widely utilized in recent studies evaluating digital platforms, information systems, and technological devices because it provides a reliable and efficient method for assessing usability even with a relatively small number of respondents. Recent research has demonstrated the effectiveness of the SUS in evaluating the usability of information systems and digital platforms, highlighting its relevance as a practical usability assessment tool.^{(9), (10)}

In this study, the SUS questionnaire was adapted to evaluate the usability of the developed Arduino microcontroller-based salted egg production device. The adapted instrument enabled the respondents to systematically assess the device in terms of operational ease, functional efficiency, and overall user satisfaction during its practical use.

2.3.3. Research Instruments

The system was evaluated using the System Usability Scale. The SUS is described as "a straightforward, ten-question scale that provides an overall perspective on subjective usability assessments". Each question offers five response options, ranging from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree." The SUS generates scores between 1 and 100, with 68 being regarded as the average score. These scores can be influenced by the complexity of both the system and the tasks users must complete before answering the SUS.

2.3.4. Scoring

The System Usability Scale is a Likert scale consisting of 10 questions that device users responded to. Research Respondents rate each statement on a scale of 1 to 5, where 5 indicates strong agreement with the statement and 1 signifies strong disagreement. Table 1 shows the scoring method for the System Usability Scale (SUS), which uses a Likert scale with 10 questions. Respondents rate each question on a scale from 1 to 5, reflecting their level of agreement with the statement. A score of 5 indicates "Strongly Agree," while a score of 1 indicates "Strongly Disagree." The table provided clarifies the qualitative descriptions corresponding to each score, ranging from strong agreement (5) to strong disagreement (1). This method is designed to quantify users' subjective assessments of a system's usability, providing a consistent way to measure user satisfaction of the website.

Table 1. Method of Scoring

Rating Scale	Qualitative Description
5	Strongly Agree
4	Agree
3	Slightly Agree
2	Slightly Disagree
1	Strongly Disagree

2.3.5. Interpretation

SUS score will be able to tell the device usability performance in the aspects of effectiveness, efficiency, and overall ease of use. Although each response yields a score on a scale of 0–100. The interpretation is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Survey Result Interpretation

SUS Score	Grade	Adjective Rating
>80.3	A	Excellent
68 – 80.3	B	Good
68	C	Okay
51-68	D	Poor
<51	E	Awful

3 Results and Discussion

This section presents the experimental findings and evaluates the performance of the developed Arduino-based automated salted egg production system. The results focus on three key aspects: (1) system performance in maintaining controlled fermentation conditions, particularly temperature stability; (2) reduction in processing time compared to traditional salting methods; and (3) usability and acceptability of the developed device among small-scale producers. The obtained results were analyzed in relation to recent literature on salted egg processing, fermentation control technologies, and automated food processing systems. Comparisons with previous studies were provided to validate the effectiveness of the proposed model and to identify areas where the findings aligned with or differed from existing reports. Both supporting and contrasting evidence from related works were discussed to establish the reliability, practical relevance, and contribution of the developed system.

Fig 3. Production Device Final Design **Legend:** A. LCD 1 – Displaying the temperature in fermenting the salted egg. B. Fan – Controlling the heat temperature inside the box. C. Flavoring Buttons – To choose what flavor you desire in fermenting in salted egg. D. 15x LED – Represent the number of days in fermenting of salted egg. E. LCD 2 – Displaying the current date and time. F. Tank – The storage of fermenting solution of salted egg.

Figure 3 presented the developed Arduino-based automated salted egg production device. Following hardware integration and calibration, experimental testing was conducted over a period of twenty-five (25) days to evaluate the stability and operational performance of the system. The selected duration was consistent with recent studies on salted egg processing that reported the use of accelerated curing and controlled brining techniques capable of reducing the conventional curing period of approximately 30 days to around 20–25 days while maintaining product quality and safety.⁽²⁾ Fresh duck eggs weighing 65–75 g and less than three days after laying were obtained from members of the Cagbonga Backyard Swine and Duck Breeders Association (CBSDBA). Standard cleaning and preparation procedures were applied prior to the salting process to ensure product hygiene and uniformity. The eggs were immersed in brine solutions with concentrations of 10%, 15%, 20%, and 25% at a constant temperature of 25 °C while maintaining a 1:1 egg-to-brine ratio (wt/wt). Three flavor variants were incorporated into the brining process, namely regular (plain), garlic-infused, and chili-infused salted eggs, to examine potential variations in sensory characteristics and product acceptability. Previous studies on salted egg processing have shown that incorporating natural flavoring agents such as garlic and chili into brining solutions can enhance aroma, taste, and consumer preference without negatively affecting the curing process.⁽¹¹⁾ The inclusion of flavored brining treatments also demonstrated the capability of the developed automated system to support diversified salted egg production.

Fig 4. Temperature monitoring comparison between the traditional salting process and the developed Arduino-based automated device during the 25-day egg curing period

Figure 4 illustrates the comparison of temperature conditions between the traditional salting process and the developed Arduino-based automated salting device throughout the 25-day curing period. The blue line represents the temperature maintained by the developed automated device, while the orange line indicates the temperature variations observed in the traditional salting method. The results show that the developed system consistently maintained a stable temperature of 25 °C during the entire curing period. In contrast, the traditional method exhibited noticeable fluctuations, with temperatures ranging from 19 °C to 27 °C. These variations indicate the absence of controlled environmental conditions in the conventional salting process.

3.1 Temperature Stability and Process Control

After the 25-day salting period, the salted eggs produced by the system were evaluated. The usability of the developed device was assessed by twenty (20) CBSDBA members using the System Usability Scale (SUS). Table 2 presents the ratings for the ten SUS items. The computed SUS score was 85.0, which corresponds to a “Very Good” usability level. Maintaining thermal stability is critical in salt diffusion and protein denaturation during egg curing. A review emphasized that temperature significantly affects salt penetration rate and yolk oil exudation in salted eggs. Their findings indicated that controlled processing conditions can

shorten curing time and improve product consistency. The present study supports this observation, as temperature regulation contributed to a 37.5% reduction in processing time, decreasing the cycle from 40 days (traditional average) to 25 days. This study demonstrated that applying pressure-assisted methods accelerated salt diffusion and reduced curing time compared to traditional immersion. While their study utilized ultrasonic-assisted pressure technology, the underlying principle enhanced mass transfer through controlled processing conditions is consistent with the present findings. Unlike pressure-based systems requiring specialized equipment, the proposed model achieves time reduction through controlled thermal regulation using a low-cost microcontroller platform, making it more accessible for small-scale producers.

3.2 Comparison with PLC-Based and Smart Fermentation Systems

A research developed a PLC-based salted egg maker using an osmotic pressure method. Their study demonstrated improved process control compared to manual salting but did not extensively address usability among rural producers.⁽⁴⁾ In contrast, the present Arduino-based system emphasizes cost efficiency, accessibility, and user acceptability, while still achieving consistent environmental regulation. The present study offers a simplified but effective alternative using standalone microcontroller-based automation, balancing technological capability with community applicability.

3.3 Processing Time Reduction

The observed reduction from 40 days to 25 days represents a 37.5% decrease in processing duration. This reduction aligns with studies showing that optimized curing conditions accelerate salt diffusion kinetics. However, unlike chemical curing enhancements, the present system achieves time reduction without modifying the chemical composition of the brine. This supports the validity of thermal regulation as an effective, non-chemical approach to improving production efficiency.

3.4 Evaluation Result

This section presents the usability evaluation results of the developed Arduino-based automated salted egg production device based on the System Usability Scale (SUS).

Table 3. System Usability Scale (SUS) Evaluation of the Developed Arduino-Based Salted Egg Production Device

#	Questions	Rating
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently.	5
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex.	2
3	I thought the system was easy to use.	5
4	I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system.	2
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated.	5
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system.	2
7	I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly.	4
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use.	2
9	I felt very confident using the system.	5
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system.	2

Table 3 presents the usability evaluation results of the developed Arduino-based automated salted egg production device using the System Usability Scale (SUS). The computed SUS score was 85.0, which falls within the “Very Good” usability category, indicating a highly acceptable level of system usability. According to SUS interpretation guidelines, scores above 80 generally reflect strong user satisfaction and a high likelihood of technology adoption. The high usability score suggests that the developed system was easy for respondents to learn, operate, and integrate into their existing salted egg production practices. The relatively low responses to negatively worded SUS items further indicate that users did not perceive the device as complex, inconsistent, or technically demanding. This result implies that the system requires minimal training and can be readily adopted by small-scale producers without the need for specialized technical knowledge. In addition to its usability advantages, the developed device effectively addressed a major limitation of traditional salted egg production, particularly the lack of temperature regulation during the curing process. By maintaining a stable fermentation temperature of 25 °C, the system ensured consistent environmental conditions throughout the salting period. Temperature stability is an important factor in salted egg production because it promotes uniform salt diffusion and improves product consistency. The controlled thermal environment also contributed to a 37.5% reduction in curing time, decreasing the production period from 40 days to 25 days.

This improvement suggests that maintaining stable temperature conditions may accelerate salt penetration and fermentation processes compared with traditional methods that rely on uncontrolled environmental conditions. Such reduction in processing time can significantly benefit small-scale producers by increasing production turnover and potential income while maintaining operational simplicity.

4 Conclusion

This study successfully developed and validated a low-cost Arduino microcontroller-based automated salted egg production system designed to improve the efficiency, consistency, and usability of traditional fermentation practices. The experimental results confirmed that the developed device maintained a stable fermentation temperature of 25 °C throughout the 25-day curing period, eliminating the irregular temperature fluctuations observed in conventional salting methods. Through automated temperature regulation, standardized salinity management, brine circulation, and controlled fermentation timing, the system reduced the production cycle from 40 days to 25 days, representing a 37.5% decrease in processing time. The findings validate that controlled thermal conditions significantly enhance salt diffusion stability and process uniformity without requiring chemical additives or high-cost pressure-assisted technologies reported in recent studies. Unlike PLC-based or IoT-intensive systems, the proposed model achieves comparable process optimization using a simplified, accessible microcontroller architecture tailored for small-scale implementation. This positions the system as a practical alternative that balances technological functionality with affordability and operational simplicity. The usability evaluation further strengthens the contribution of this research. The System Usability Scale (SUS) score of 85.0, classified as “Very Good,” indicates high user acceptance, strong learnability, and minimal perceived complexity among members of the Cagbonga Backyard Swine and Duck Breeders Association (CBSDBA). The integration of technical validation with community-level usability assessment represents a distinctive contribution, as many automation studies emphasize performance metrics without evaluating adoption feasibility. The novelty of this study lies in the integration of temperature-controlled fermentation and salinity-regulated brining within a single, low-cost Arduino-based platform specifically designed for traditional salted egg production. By combining environmental regulation, automation, and user-centered validation, the research bridges the gap between advanced food processing technologies and community-scale agricultural practices. From a practical perspective, the developed system offers strong potential for deployment in farmer cooperatives, livelihood programs, and small-scale food enterprises seeking to increase production turnover while maintaining product consistency. The reduction in curing time directly translates into increased production capacity and improved income opportunities for rural producers. Future research may focus on integrating wireless monitoring or IoT-based data logging for remote supervision, incorporating adaptive control algorithms to optimize salinity and temperature dynamically, and conducting physicochemical and sensory evaluations to further validate product quality improvements. Scaling studies may also be conducted to assess performance in larger production batches and explore commercialization feasibility.

References

- 1) Wang X, Gao Z, Xiao H, Wang Y, Bai J. Enhanced mass transfer of osmotic dehydration and changes in microstructure of pickled salted egg under pulsed pressure. *Journal of Food Engineering*. 2013;117(1):141–150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2013.02.013>.
- 2) Su Y, Chen Z, Li J, Chang C, Gu L, Yang Y. Characterization of salted egg yolk flavoring prepared by enzyme hydrolysis and microwave irradiation. *Food Chemistry*. 2021;338:127913. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2020.127913>.
- 3) Ganesan P, Kaewmanee T, Benjakul S, Baharin BS. Comparative study on the nutritional value of pidan and salted duck egg. *Korean Journal for Food Science of Animal Resources*. 2014;34(1):1–6. <https://doi.org/10.5851/kosfa.2014.34.1.1>.
- 4) Masfufiah I, Firmansyah V, Muharom S, Firmansyah RA, Pambudi WS. Development of salted egg maker by using PLC based on osmotic pressure method. *Elkha: Jurnal Teknik Elektro*. 2024;16(1):15–20. <https://doi.org/10.26418/elkha.v16i1.69634>.
- 5) Deep A, Jindal N, Prasad K. Development of microcontroller-based versatile device for process monitoring and control applications in food processing industries. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*. 2026. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13197-026-06623-w>.
- 6) Zafía A, Novantoro SD, Utomo AD. Sistem monitoring proses pengasinan telur asin berbasis IoT. *JlPI (Jurnal Ilmiah Penelitian dan Pembelajaran Informatika)*. 2024;9(2). <https://doi.org/10.29100/jlpi.v9i2.4689>.
- 7) Fitrialdi F. Implementation of an IoT system in the teaching factory: Optimization of the salted fish drying process. *Syntax Literate: Jurnal Ilmiah Indonesia*. 2024;9(11). <https://doi.org/10.36418/syntax-literate.v9i11.51705>.
- 8) Xiao C, Zhang Y, Gong T, Guan R. A comparative study of pickled salted eggs by positive and negative pressure-ultrasonic method. *Foods*. 2023;12(7):1477. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods12071477>.
- 9) Akbar I. Penerapan system usability scale dalam pengukuran kegunaan website SMKN 13 Bandung. *INTERNAL: Information System Journal*. 2024;7(1). <https://doi.org/10.32627/internal.v7i1.865>.
- 10) Irawan Y, Suryani FB, Wanabuliandari S, Muzid S. System usability scale (SUS) model in evaluating internal quality audit systems for accreditation process optimization. *Journal of Applied Informatics and Computing*. 2025;9(2). <https://doi.org/10.30871/jaic.v9i2.9210>.
- 11) Zhang X, Wu Y, Liu J. Influence of spice and herbal additives on the physicochemical and sensory properties of salted duck eggs. *Foods*. 2023;12(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods12040852>.